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High-performance carbon-based supercapacitors

To cite this article: Ivan Dědek *et al* 2025 *2D Mater.* **12** 043004

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2D Materials

PERSPECTIVE

High-performance carbon-based supercapacitors

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
25 April 2025

REVISED
22 June 2025

ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
31 July 2025

PUBLISHED
20 August 2025

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Keywords: supercapacitor, activated carbon, graphene, performance, manufacturing

Abstract

Carbon-based supercapacitors (SCs) have emerged as promising candidates for high-power, fast-charging energy storage, bridging the performance gap between traditional capacitors and batteries. This perspective explores the current landscape and future direction of carbon-based electric double-layer capacitors, focusing on activated carbon, graphene, and their derivatives. We highlight key performance-limiting factors in real-world devices including electrode composition, electrolyte selection, and device form factor. Special attention is given to sustainable materials sourcing, low-temperature and high-temperature operation, and the transition toward greener electrode processing. While curved graphene has already demonstrated successful scalability from lab to commercial device formats, other promising advanced materials, e.g. nitrogen doping graphene and graphdiyne, are still in the early stages of this transition. Although these materials offer outstanding performance at the fundamental level, integrating them into practical, scalable SC architectures continues to pose significant challenges. A systems-level optimization, encompassing electrodes' architecture, manufacturing compatibility, and novel electrolytes, is crucial to unlock the full potential of SCs. By integrating material innovation with scalable engineering, carbon-based SCs can meet the growing energy demands of modern applications, from portable electronics to aerospace and grid storage.

1. Introduction

Advancing electrochemical energy storage systems is vital for achieving the United Nations affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy goal [1]. This involves enhancing the performance, safety, and environmental friendliness of these devices while reducing their cost. The development of highly capacitive materials and advanced technologies is particularly critical for industries such as automotive, aerospace, power generation, heavy machinery, and electric tools, where efficient and robust energy storage is key to meet increasing energy demands [2–4].

Electric double-layer capacitors (EDLC) represent available energy storage technology with remarkable qualities, such as fast charging/discharging capability

and extra-long cycle-life [5–7]. Supercapacitors (SCs, also known as ultracapacitors) store energy at the electrode–electrolyte interface through EDLC mechanism, which involves fast and highly reversible physical processes. This makes SCs particularly suitable for applications requiring high power density [8], especially in scenarios demanding frequent and rapid power delivery and uptake. Additionally, since SCs do not rely on electrochemical reactions during charging and discharging, they pose a lower safety risk compared to rechargeable lithium-ion batteries [9, 10].

The performance parameters SCs depend on various factors, which will be discussed in detail later; however, the choice of electrode materials is among the most critical aspects. Various advanced electrode materials have been explored to enhance the

performance of SCs, among them, activated carbons (ACs) and graphene, have been successfully utilized [11]. Currently available commercial SCs typically operate at voltages up to 3.0 V⁵ and employ carbon-based electrodes paired with organic electrolytes. Key performance metrics such as gravimetric capacitance, energy and power densities reach up to approximately 9 F g⁻¹, 11 Wh kg⁻¹, and 28 kW kg⁻¹, respectively. A noticeable gap exists between the material properties reported in scientific literature and the actual performance of commercial SCs. The gap is given by several factors, which include differences in testing configurations, device form factor constraints, and not unified benchmarking protocols. Lab-scale studies often report gravimetric capacitance and energy density based solely on the mass of active material, neglecting the contribution of current collectors, binders, electrolytes, separators, and packaging. In contrast, commercial device metrics are evaluated at the full-cell level. In this perspective, we examine the properties of carbon-based SCs and explore potential directions for future development in this rapidly evolving field.

2. Key parameters of a SC

The performance of a SC is evaluated based on several key parameters, among which cycle life, power density, and energy density are considered the most critically important [12]. These parameters are often the primary focus of industry, although, in academic research, specific capacitance is frequently emphasized as a central metric. The choice of electrolyte plays a defining role in determining the voltage window. The voltage window defines the maximum operating voltage range and directly impacts the achievable energy density. In contrast, the internal resistance, referred to as equivalent series resistance (ESR), influences the round trip efficiency of charge and discharge processes and affects both power density and heat generation. The performance characteristics of SC are governed by a range of internal factors (figure 1). Among these, the selection of active electrode material and electrolyte is particularly critical. The electrode material and its mass loading directly affect specific capacitance and the ESR [13]. Additionally, various additives, which are introduced to enhance electrode's mechanical stability and electrical conductivity, can also affect the overall performance of the SC device. In summary, the material composition, electrolyte, and form factor collectively determine the final properties of SC. Conversely, these internal parameters can be tailored to tune the device's performance characteristics [13, 14].

The complexity of factors influencing the performance of SC devices contributes significantly to the gap often observed between the performance characteristics of individual components, typically

Figure 1. The schematic illustrates composition features that determine the performance characteristics of a supercapacitor (SC).

the electrode materials, and the actual performance of the assembled device. It is important to note that the key parameters such as capacitance, power density, and energy density are dependent on the current density (e.g. as current density increases, energy density typically decreases). Moreover, performance data reported in the scientific literature is often based on three-electrode configurations, which do not accurately represent the geometry or conditions of real SC devices. In contrast, two-electrode setups offer a more realistic assessment, as they better mimic actual device architecture. Additionally, specific performance values in publications are frequently normalized to the mass of the active electrode material alone, whereas commercial device specifications are usually based on the total mass or volume of the entire SC unit. It is worth noting that the electrode material typically accounts for only a few percent, and at most a few dozen percent, of the total mass of the SC.

Electrode thickness and packing density introduce further disparity. Thin-film electrodes used in lab tests (often $<10 \mu\text{m}$) can artificially yield higher capacitance due to full ion accessibility. In contrast, practical devices require thicker electrodes ($\sim 50\text{--}100 \mu\text{m}$ total thickness of electrode material coated on both sides of the current collector) to store meaningful energy, resulting in capacitance drop by a factor of 2–3. Materials like graphene [15–20], while exhibiting quantum capacitance of 520 F g^{-1} (calculated from double-layer capacitance of $\sim 21 \mu\text{F g}^{-1}$ measured for graphene on silicon/SiO₂ substrate in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate, using a three-electrode configuration [21, 22]), often suffer from poor packing density ($<0.5 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) and restacking, which dilute their performance at

the device level. Volumetric energy density is also substantially lower for nanostructured carbons due to excessive porosity. For instance, a graphene electrode with 85 Wh kg^{-1} gravimetric energy may translate to only $\sim 5 \text{ Wh L}^{-1}$ at the device level [23], comparable to standard AC-based SCs. All these factors must be carefully considered when comparing material-level research findings with the performance metrics of marketed SCs [24–27].

3. AC, graphene, and graphene derivatives as electrode materials

Carbonaceous materials, including AC, graphene, and graphene derivatives [28–32], are widely used as active materials for SC electrodes due to their high surface area, electrical conductivity, low density, and composition based on of Earth-abundant element [28]. AC is readily accessible and can be produced from a variety of biomass sources [33] such as coconut husks [34, 35], leaves [36–38], coal char [18, 39], and wood [40, 41], using either chemical or physical activation methods [42]. These biomass feedstock are typically chosen for their high carbon content, which is essential for generating AC with favorable surface area and porosity. The conversion of bio-waste to AC generally involves pyrolysis, which develops the required porous structure. Beyond biomass, plastic waste has recently emerged as a promising alternative precursor for producing AC [43–49]. AC derived from plastic waste offers a compelling pathway for creating high-value electrode materials for SCs [44, 49, 50]. This approach supports circular economy principles and aligns with sustainable development goals by transforming carbon-rich waste into advanced functional materials. Future research should focus on integrating AC production with CO/CO₂ valorization strategies, as carbon oxides are significant by-products of pyrolytic processes.

ACs have an irregular and imperfect arrangement of microcrystalline or amorphous carbon [51]. They offer numerous benefits, including a simple fabrication process and an enormous specific surface area (SSA). The highly porous structure of ACs increases the overall SSA and pore volume while decreasing density and weight. These properties make ACs ideal electrode material for SCs. The SSA is critical as it determines the number of active sites available for ion adsorption, but pure ACs are hydrophobic due to the lack of functionalities that would enhance the wettability and hydrophilicity. Various strategies, such as surface functionalization [52], preparation of composites [53], or nitrogen doping (N-doping) [54], can be a viable strategy, which is frequently employed to enhance the wettability of the carbon surface, thereby lowering surface tension

and improving ion access to the pores. Additionally, the N-doping can introduce pseudocapacitive effects, which can further enhance the capacitance [55].

Graphene represents an exceptional material for SC electrodes [56] due to its large SSA and high conductivity. It can be synthesized through various approaches bottom-up or top-down [21, 57]. Realization of SC based on pure graphene is challenging due to its restacking tendency and high hydrophobicity [58]. Restacking significantly reduces the accessible surface area by limiting pore availability, thereby hindering the diffusion of electrolyte ions to the electrode surface [59]. This issue can be mitigated by introducing curvature to the graphene structure, which creates microporosity and enhances ion accessibility [60]. Curved graphene demonstrated promising performance, delivering a specific energy density of 85.6 Wh kg^{-1} at room temperature and up to 136 Wh kg^{-1} at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (measured at a current density of 1 A g^{-1}). A cylindrical (wound) demonstrator device utilizing curved graphene and featuring a nominal capacitance of 5000 F achieved a specific energy of 8.4 Wh kg^{-1} , an energy density of 12.2 Wh L^{-1} , and maintained 77% of its original capacitance over extended cycling [61].

Optimizing carbon-based electrode materials parameters such as SSA, pore structure, doping and surface functionalization are essential for improving the performance in SCs. Optimizing pore structure in carbon-based electrodes is crucial for enhancing SC performance. Research has shown that sub nanometer pores can exhibit an unexpected increase in specific capacitance, as ions partially shed their solvation shells to enter these confined spaces, leading to denser ion packing. This phenomenon, confirmed by molecular dynamics simulations and experimental studies, underscores the importance of tailoring pore sizes to match ion dimensions, thereby maximizing energy storage efficiency [59, 62–64]. However, when ionic liquids (ILs) are confined within these nanoporous structures, ion transport significantly slows compared to the bulk electrolyte. Interestingly, such confinement also induces a ‘premelting’ effect, maintaining IL in a fluid state far below their normal freezing points, broadening the operational temperature range of SCs. Additionally, nanoconfinement has been shown experimentally to suppress thermal decomposition of ILs effectively at temperatures below $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, highlighting the unique stability conferred by nanoscale environments. Hierarchical carbon structures combining micropores for high capacitance with mesopores to improve ion mobility and electrolyte fluidity are crucial for achieving optimized energy storage across wide temperature ranges [65–68].

Graphene’s wettability can be increased by N-doping, which could promote the development

of N-doped graphene with interesting properties. However, due to graphene's high chemical inertness, direct functionalization remains challenging. This limitation can be overcome by utilizing fluorographene (FG) as a reactive intermediate for the synthesis of graphene derivatives [32, 69]. For instance, treatment of FG with sodium azide yields a material that combines graphene-like sp^2 layers with tetrahedral carbon-carbon bonds and a high level (16%) of N-doping. Featuring C-C diamond-like bonding among N-doped graphene layers and an exceptionally high mass density of 2.8 g cm^{-3} , this material serves as an outstanding ion host, achieving up to 200 Wh L^{-1} (power 2.6 kW L^{-1}) in two-electrode setup [70].

Graphene-based hybrid materials, including composites with MXenes [71], metal-organic frameworks [72], and covalent organic frameworks [73] have shown promising pseudocapacitive behavior and high energy storage performance in laboratory-scale studies. These hybrids leverage the high conductivity and surface area of graphene alongside the redox-active or porous nature of the secondary material. However, translating these advances into commercially viable technologies remains a challenge. Although progress has been made in synthesis techniques, issues such as high production costs, limited scalability, and batch-to-batch variability persist. In comparison to AC, which is inexpensive and industrially mature, and curved or defective graphene, which can be produced via more scalable approaches, graphene-based hybrids are not yet at a stage of broad industrial readiness. Nonetheless, ongoing research into cost-effective, scalable fabrication methods and performance optimization continues to push these materials closer to practical applications in next-generation SCs.

A distant cousin of graphene, the graphdiyne, and its derivatives are considered as another emerging class of materials [74]. While graphdiyne exhibits promising properties for SC applications, including high electrical conductivity, large surface area, and abundant active sites, it is not yet ready for widespread commercial use [75]. Key challenges remain, particularly in scaling up its mass production with high reproducibility. Current synthesis methods often lack the scalability and control necessary for practical manufacturing, hindering the consistent production of high-quality graphdiyne materials [76, 77]. Furthermore, despite encouraging laboratory results regarding cycling stability [78] and energy density, further improvements are needed to meet the stringent demands for long-term reliability and performance in real-world SC devices [79, 80]. Research is ongoing to address these synthesis and performance limitations, aiming to unlock the full potential of graphdiyne and its derivatives for advanced energy storage.

4. Device form factor and the performance gap

Currently marketed devices using carbon-based materials demonstrated energy densities of $5\text{--}8 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$ [81], while the scientific literature reports on energy densities of up to 149 Wh kg^{-1} [82–84]. A noticeable gap persists between the performance in laboratory conditions and in real-world SC devices. This discrepancy can be attributed to the electrodes' preparation methods and unoptimized devices architecture. Pouch-type cells are generally preferred in space or height-constrained applications due to their high performance in thin, low-profile packages. They offer uniform distribution and a flat configuration, ensuring optimal contact and ion transport.

In contrast, wound cell construction, which employs cylindrical cans, provides scalable mass manufacturing at lower costs. This allows for case flexibility, ranging from miniature to large cans with high energy density content. Consequently, wound cells dominate the majority of the market, while pouch types are favored in applications requiring minimal space. The construction of wound cells requires electrodes with a high areal mass loading to maximize device energy storage, but simultaneously with sufficient mechanical integrity to avoid delamination during the rolling process or under repeated charge/discharge cycling.

The global SC market is expanding rapidly, driven by the increasing demand in automotive systems, renewable energy integration, and industrial automation. To meet these diverse and evolving application requirements, SCs must overcome several technical and regulatory challenges related to performance, compliance, and safety. High power density remains one of their defining advantages, making them particularly suitable for applications such as electric vehicle regenerative braking and grid stabilization, where rapid charge-discharge cycles are essential. However, enhancing energy density is critical for SCs to compete with advanced battery technologies, especially in sectors requiring compact yet long-lasting energy storage. Long operational life and stability, often exceeding 500 000 cycles with minimal capacitance loss, are especially important in industrial and grid applications, where longevity and reliability directly impact system efficiency and maintenance costs.

SCs also offer important advantages in terms of safety and regulatory compliance. Unlike batteries, they do not rely on electrochemical reactions and therefore present a much lower fire risk. This intrinsic safety profile makes them attractive for applications with stringent reliability requirements. Still, achieving these safety benefits in practice necessitates adherence to recognized manufacturing standards. Compliance with ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 ensures

quality management and environmental responsibility, while UL certification confirms conformance with rigorous safety criteria. Together, these certifications enhance confidence in the reliability and performance of SCs in end-use environments.

Adaptability to specific application needs is another essential aspect of SC design. Devices must function reliably across broad temperature ranges, from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, for automotive and aerospace applications. Emerging flexible and ultrathin formats, enabled by gel polymer electrolytes, support integration into compact electronics, including IoT and wearable devices. Furthermore, hybrid energy storage systems that combine SCs with lithium-ion batteries demand careful matching of voltage characteristics and thermal profiles to optimize performance and durability.

To facilitate high-throughput production and reduce assembly costs, SCs must also be compatible with surface-mount technology (SMT) and withstand reflow soldering temperatures of up to $260\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This requirement poses a significant technical challenge, as most SC types are not yet robust enough to survive such thermal processes. However, the development of reflow-compatible SMT SCs would mark a major step toward their adoption in high-volume electronics manufacturing.

Environmental compliance is non-negotiable for global market success. SCs must meet restriction of hazardous substances and registration, evaluation, authorization and restriction of chemicals directive, including lead-free design and exclusion of substances of very high concerns (SVHCs). Beyond basic compliance, manufacturers are expected to evaluate and minimize environmental impact throughout the product life cycle. This includes conducting comprehensive life cycle assessments, selecting recyclable and non-toxic materials, and developing end-of-life recycling strategies to support sustainability goals.

Finally, scalability and cost-efficiency in manufacturing are vital to enable broader adoption. Automated, high-yield production processes must balance affordability with quality and environmental standards. While research continues to close the energy density gap between SCs and batteries, commercial success will depend not only on technical progress but also on rigorous compliance with industry and environmental standards. Integrating advanced materials with scalable engineering and regulatory alignment will be essential for positioning SCs as key components in next-generation energy storage systems.

5. Emerging directions: micro-SCs and device miniaturization

Beyond large-scale devices, micro-SCs (MSCs) based on graphene and ACs are gaining attention as a

key emerging technology for powering or protecting next-generation miniaturized electronics [56, 85]. These devices leverage the same electrochemical principles as traditional SCs but are fabricated using techniques such as laser writing [86], screen printing, or inkjet deposition, enabling integration onto chip-level systems. MSCs are typically designed as either sandwich-type or interdigital structures. The interdigital design offers superior integration flexibility and reduced ion diffusion lengths, which are advantageous for compact, high-performance systems. Recent advances in flexible substrates and laser-patterned microarchitectures, such as Kirigami-inspired structures, further improve mechanical adaptability for wearable applications [87].

MSCs benefit from short ion diffusion paths and high power density but achieving sufficient areal or volumetric energy densities remains a challenge. Their performance strongly depends on both the intrinsic properties of the materials and the precise control over device geometry, suggesting that advances in microfabrication techniques will be essential for their future adoption. As MSCs are increasingly integrated into multifunctional systems such as sensors, energy harvesters, and biomedical devices, improving their compatibility and miniaturization will be critical for enabling real-world applications [87].

6. Electrolytes setting performance limits

EDLCs are class of SCs that operate based on the reversible adsorption and desorption of ions at the electrode–electrolyte interface. This physical process, also known as electrical double-layer formation, relies on coulombic interactions rather than faradic redox reactions, making it significantly faster than the electrochemical processes in batteries [7]. Hence, the nature of the electrolyte largely governs the overall performance of the SC. Electrolytes used in SCs can be categorized into liquid types, including aqueous, organic, and ILs, as well as solid, and semi-solid (gel) electrolytes [88]. The properties of the electrolyte, including ion mobility, ion size, pH, viscosity, and the operating potential window, directly affect the overall SC performance characteristics, such as energy density, and cycling stability [89]. For optimal functionality, an ideal electrolyte should possess high ionic conductivity, a wide electrochemical window, and thermal stability across a wide operating temperature range (ideally from $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Additionally, low volatility, low flammability, and environmental compatibility are desirable for practical deployment. Ion transport properties affected by viscosity, diffusion coefficient, and ionic conductivity, determine how efficiently ions can migrate to and from the electrode surfaces during charge and discharge cycles. High viscosity and low diffusion coefficients

hinder ion movement, leading to increased ESR, slower response times, and reduced power density. Conversely, low-viscosity electrolytes with high ionic mobility promote rapid charge transfer and enable better rate capability and energy delivery. A stable and wide electrochemical window for normal operation of the electrolyte systems is critically important for maximizing SC performance. The broader the voltage window, the more energy the device can store, as the energy density of a SC scales with the square of the cell voltage ($E \propto V^2$). In practical terms, the stored energy can be visualized as the area under representing voltage profiles measured as galvanostatic discharge curves [51, 90, 91].

Aqueous electrolytes are inherently limited by the electrochemical stability window of water, which constrains the operating voltage to approximately ± 1.23 V. Exceeding this limit initiates water electrolysis, resulting in the evolution of hydrogen gas at negative potentials (around -1.23 V) and oxygen at positive potentials (around 1.23 V). This gas formation leads to undesired bubbles generation, which is particularly problematic in sealed or compact device configurations. In contrast, organic electrolytes provide a significantly wider operational voltage range, typically around 2.7 V, enabling higher energy and power densities [90].

ILs have emerged as a promising class of electrolytes for SCs due to their unique physicochemical properties. These salts, which are in the liquid state at (or near) room temperature, exhibit low volatility, high thermal stability, and a broad electrochemical window, often extending beyond 3 V, and in some cases reaching up to 4 V [92]. These properties make ILs particularly attractive for applications requiring high energy and power densities [93]. ILs are also explored for their capacity to operate over extended temperature ranges. While they generally maintain thermal stability up to 300 °C– 400 °C, their stability is highly sensitive to impurities such as water, halide residues, and metal ions, as well as to specific structural features, particularly the presence of halide-based anions, which can significantly reduce their thermal resilience. In addition, the high ionic conductivity of ILs supports efficient ion transport, further improving the SC performance, particularly rate capability which boosts power density and resistance at the electrode–electrolyte interface, which impacts the overall ESR. However, ILs are often more viscous than conventional organic electrolytes, which can hinder ion diffusion and affect rate capability. This limitation can be mitigated by blending ILs with low-viscosity solvents such as propylene carbonate (PC) or acetonitrile (ACN) to improve ionic mobility. Overall, the combination of a wide voltage window, high thermal stability, and design flexibility positions ILs as a highly attractive electrolyte choice

for next-generation, high-performance SC technologies, however, their high cost, associated with their complicated synthesis and requirements for high-purity reagents and purification prevent them from being widely used [93, 94].

7. Extending operating temperature range

SCs are increasingly demanded for applications with limited or no thermal control, including space-based avionics systems, electric aircraft, unmanned aerial vehicles, and electric or hybrid vehicles. However, current commercial SCs typically operate within a narrow temperature range of approximately -40 °C to $+70$ °C, primarily due to limitations posed by the used electrolyte. Recent research has demonstrated SCs operating between -100 °C and $+200$ °C (table 1). The challenge is not just about extending the operating temperature, but also about ensuring that the SCs can withstand the reflow process during PCB assembly, which is an arguably even more important requirement that would enable automated board mounting. In other words, SCs in metal can packages with SMD terminals may be capable of enduring lead-free reflow at a peak temperature of 260 °C, similarly, to typically used aluminum capacitors. At temperatures below 0 °C, electrolyte viscosity increases sharply, leading to reduced ionic conductivity and slower ion diffusion. This results in diminished capacitance, elevated ESR, and compromised energy and power densities. Conventional organic electrolytes such as tetraethyl ammonium tetrafluoroborate salt (TEA BF₄) dissolved in ACN and PC face performance constraints due to their freezing points of -46 °C and -49 °C for ACN and PC, respectively, which drastically reduces their utility in cryogenic environments. Even above these freezing points, ion mobility declines sharply, further exacerbating performance losses. To overcome these limitations, advanced electrolyte formulations are under development. One promising strategy involves blending ACN with low-freezing-point organic co-solvents, such as methyl formate, methyl acetate, ethyl acetate, or 1,3-dioxolane (DIOX) [95]. These mixtures aim to reduce viscosity and enhance ion transport at cryogenic temperatures, extending the functional range of SCs in demanding environments.

Developing SCs capable of operating at extremely low temperatures, such as -100 °C and below, remains a significant scientific and engineering challenge [96]. However, application such as space technologies specifically demand SCs that can function reliably under such extreme conditions [97–99]. Using a eutectic mixture of IL as the electrolyte enables SC efficient operation down to -100 °C, achieving a capacitance of 164 F g⁻¹, compared to 182 F g⁻¹ at 60 °C [95]. Another promising

Table 1. The performance characteristics of SCs based on data collected from two-electrode setup reported in the literature, PW = potential window.

Operating temperature	Capacitance	Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)/ Curr. dens. (A g ⁻¹)	Retention (c = cycles)	PW (V)	Energy power power density	Electrolyte	References
-100 °C to + 60 °C	164 F g ⁻¹ at -100 °C 182 F g ⁻¹ at 60 °C	5 mV s ⁻¹ 5 mV s ⁻¹	99.3% at -60 °C (5 A g ⁻¹ ; (10 000 c) 92% at +60 °C (10 000 c)	2.5	N/A	(MeEt ₃ N ⁺) in ACN/DIOX	[95]
-50 °C to + 80 °C	125 F cm ⁻³ (109 F g ⁻¹ at RT 106 F cm ⁻³ (92 F g ⁻¹) at -50 °C	5 mV s ⁻¹ 5 mV s ⁻¹	84% at -60 °C (5 mV s ⁻¹ ; 200 c	3.5	N/A	BMPBF ₄ in BMIBF ₄	[128]
RT to + 200 °C	1007 F g ⁻¹ at 200 °C 53 F g ⁻¹ at RT	1 A g ⁻¹ 100 mV s ⁻¹	≈90% at 200 °C at 5 A g ⁻¹ (10 000 c)	1.5	1134 Wh kg ⁻¹ at 200 °C at 1 A g ⁻¹ 4.3 kW kg ⁻¹ at 200 °C	EMI-TFSI	[104]
RT to + 200 °C	165 F g ⁻¹ at 200 °C 15 F g ⁻¹ at RT	1.5 A g ⁻¹ 0.1 A g ⁻¹	≈85% (500 c) at 200 °C at 2.5 A g ⁻¹	1	N/A	BMIMCl ionogel	[102]
-40 °C to + 100 °C	8 F g ⁻¹ at -40 °C 76 F g ⁻¹ at RT 85 F g ⁻¹ at 100 °C	5 A g ⁻¹ 5 A g ⁻¹ 5 A g ⁻¹	83% (5000 c) at 1 A g ⁻¹ at -40 °C	4 3 3	≈20 kW kg ⁻¹ ≈ 12 Wh kg ⁻¹ at RT	TEABF ₄ in PC	[100]

strategy for enhancing low-temperature performance involves maximizing electrolyte accessibility during SC operation [100]. For instance, spray coating of an ink composed of single- and few-layer graphene flakes, combined with a binary electrolyte mixture of γ -butyrolactone and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [101] enabled stable SC operation at $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ achieving an energy density of 43.9 Wh kg^{-1} at a power density 200 W kg^{-1} .

At the opposite end of the temperature spectrum, high temperatures also pose significant challenge for SC performance. As mentioned above, elevated temperatures accelerate electrolyte degradation, compromising both stability and efficiency. At extreme conditions approaching or exceeding $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, IL-based electrolytes have shown particular promise, offering dual functionality as both electrolyte and separator within a single, thermally robust composite structure [102–104]. Carbon-based electrodes, especially those incorporating graphene, tend to retain their structural integrity under such conditions, thereby shifting the primary challenge toward mitigating degradation at the electrolyte–electrode interface [102]. At elevated temperatures (typically above $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ – $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), conventional solvents used for electrolyte solutions are prone to rapid evaporation or decomposition, while standard polymer separators and binders can often melt or degrade. Beyond $\sim 120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, electrolyte degradation accelerates dramatically, and commonly used polyolefin-based separators and binders such as PVDF lose their structural integrity at around $130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $177\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively [105, 106]. To address these limitations, advanced thermal-resistant materials have been developed. These include separators made from glass fiber mats, ceramic fiber papers, or thermostable polyimide (Kapton), as well as high-temperature binders, like polybenzimidazole and polytetrafluorethylene, which offer improved stability and durability under extreme thermal conditions.

8. Safer solvent systems for electrode fabrication

In the fabrication of SC electrodes, N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) is widely used due to its excellent ability to disperse carbon-based active materials, facilitating the production of uniform slurries and well-structured electrode films. Nevertheless, NMP poses significant health and environmental risks: it is classified by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [107] as a developmental toxicant and designated as a reproductive toxin and SVHC by the European Union [108, 109]. These concerns have spurred considerable research over the past decade to identify safer and more sustainable solvent

alternatives. However, despite these efforts, no substitute has yet been able to replicate the performance characteristics of NMP fully. Aqueous electrode processing offers a green alternative to NMP, but challenges include finding suitable water-soluble binders with high thermal stability and strong adhesion [110–113]. Also, processing equipment must avoid corrosion, and water can corrode aluminum current collectors unless pH is controlled. In parallel with aqueous-based approaches, organic solvents were investigated for slurry preparation. However, significant efforts have focused on batteries, and the field of SC electrodes has only been explored to a limited extent [114–117]. Although the search for safer solvent alternatives in SC electrode fabrication has received relatively limited scientific attention, it has high industrial relevance [118]. The continued reliance on NMP, despite its known health and environmental hazards, presents regulatory and operational challenges for manufacturers [108, 119].

9. Perspective and needs

9.1. Active electrode materials

Future development of carbon-based SC electrodes will increasingly rely on sustainability and circular economy goals. Biomass-derived AC, produced from biowaste sources, offer sustainable and scalable option, nevertheless, future research should explore its integration with CO/CO₂ valorization chain during pyrolysis. Plastic waste has also emerged as a promising AC precursor, aligning with circular economy goals by converting carbon-rich waste into high-value materials [19]. Among carbon-based materials, graphene and N-doped graphene [54, 70] stand out for their extraordinary electrochemical performance, however, realization of SC based on such materials is challenging due to upscaling procedures of synthesis. A particular effort should be paid to low-cost and safe scalable processes for production of such materials.

While the active electrode material can account for up to 30% of a SC's total composition [23], the remaining components, i.e. binders, solvents, electrolytes, separators, current collectors, and form factor, are no less important. Therefore, any improvements for industrial application must take into account not only the use of active materials with better performance, but also the optimization of all other components within the SC itself. Future effort should also focus on manufacturing processes that enable double-sided electrode coating on thin current collectors, with the aim to maximize active material loading while maintaining sufficient mechanical integrity and ensuring compatibility with roll-to-roll fabrication methods utilized for wound-cell SC architectures (figure 2).

Figure 2. Scheme showing process of SC manufacturing.

9.2. Electrolytes

Electrolytes are especially critical, as they influence not just energy and power density but also thermal stability and safety. ILs, eutectic mixtures, and polymer hybrids are being tailored for broad electrochemical stability, non-volatility, and temperature resilience. Hybrid electrolytes that combine different conduction mechanisms (protonic, lithium-ion, etc) are on the rise—for example, gel polymers doped with ILs or acids to leverage both solid-state stability and liquid-like ion mobility. The high-entropy electrolyte concept (mixing 5+ solvents) can represent a promising direction for all-weather SCs, having already shown dramatically improved low-temperature performance without sacrificing high-temperature operation [120]. Another pathway is ‘water-in-salt’ (WIS) and ‘salt-in-polymer’ electrolytes for safer and non-flammable devices [121]. By incorporating ultrahigh salt concentrations or polymer hosts, these systems offer wide voltage windows and improved thermal stability, with recent innovations (like the ACN/WIS mixture) [122, 123] mitigating their low-temperature limitations. In summary, designing electrolytes for extreme temperatures is of scientific and industrial interest [96]. The continued convergence of materials science and electrochemistry is expected to yield electrolytes that give SCs the elusive combination of fast, safe, and reliable performance from the cryogenic regime to well over 100 °C, providing applications in aerospace, electric vehicles, grid storage, and beyond.

9.3. Active electrode materials

Aqueous electrode processing has been successfully demonstrated at the industrial scale [61]. Nevertheless, challenges remain particularly in identifying suitable water-soluble binders for other high-performance carbon-based materials that offer high thermal stability and strong adhesion in the lab-scale. In parallel with aqueous-based approaches, green organic solvents that enable proper dispersion of components and effective adhesion to current collectors are highly desirable. Promising candidates include γ -valerolactone [117, 124] however, it is classified as

a drug precursor and considered a controlled substance, which may impede its industrial utilization. Other promising candidates are dihydrolevoglucosenone (commercially known as Cyrene) [125, 126] and N-butyl-2-pyrrolidone (trade name TamiSolve). Although Cyrene exhibits considerable potential as a suitable alternative to NMP, its high surface tension and viscosity often lead to poor wettability and adhesion, resulting in delamination from a current collector [127]. Moreover, while elevated temperature (e.g. 90 °C) can partially improve PVDF dissolution, they may introduce complications into the coating process. The other green solvent, TamiSolve, has a high boiling point (~ 241 °C), low vapor pressure, and excellent solvency power for a wide range of polymers. To the best of our knowledge, TamiSolve has not yet been explored for electrode fabrication. Finally, the relatively high cost of green solvents remains a significant barrier to large-scale industrial adoption.

9.4. Standardization and regulatory alignment

Despite extensive research into carbon-based SCs, standardization and rigorous compliance with established industry norms, such as IEC62391-1 for performance characterization, UL810A for safety assessment, IEC62391-2 and MIL STD 202 for (high temperature) lifecycle testing, as well as environmental and durability evaluations following IEC 60 068-2-27, IEC61373, MIL STD 202, Method 103, and ESCC 226 300 for low pressure conditions, remain largely overlooked in scientific publications. Highlighting and adhering to these standardized testing methodologies is crucial to bridge the gap between laboratory research and industrial reliability, ensuring carbon-based SC consistently meet stringent performance and safety requirements for real world applications.

10. Summary

This perspective highlights the critical factors influencing the performance of carbon-based SCs, particularly those utilizing AC, graphene and its derivatives. While material innovations including advanced

AC, N-doped graphene and graphdiyne offer promising electrochemical properties, real-world device performance remains constrained by limitations in electrode design, electrolyte selection, and scalable manufacturing. Key challenges include bridging the gap between lab-scale performance and commercial viability, extending the operational temperature range, and transitioning to greener processing methods. Moving forward, a holistic approach, i.e. integrating advances in materials, electrolytes, and engineering design, is essential to unlock the full potential of SCs for modern energy systems.

Data availability statement

No new data were created or analysed in this study.

Acknowledgment

We thank to the European Union for funding via EIC Transition project TRANS2DCHEM (No. 101057616). The work was also supported from ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587). M.O. also acknowledges financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH—Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries Project Number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition.

Conflict-of interest statement

MO, VŠ, and TZ are shareholders in ATOMIVER, s.r.o., a company focused on the manufacturing of N-doped graphene for SC applications. LP serves as the President of the Board at Itelcond S.R.L., a company specializing in the production of high-capacitance aluminum electrolytic capacitors.

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